

Blockchain and Game

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Abstract

1. Introduction

Worked at Japanese game company Neverland Ltd., had a experience for client side program, server side program, game design, project management. u Worked at Taipei, for project management and game development.

Establish Platinum Egg Inc. u Worked with more than 100 game projects, total user numbers is more than 1million users. u Can do programming, game design, project management, and many things!

Blockchain project start, and especially focusing to blockchain game.

Focusing Crypto Derby Project and co-working some blockchain foundation.

Author biography

Nariya Takemura Nariya Takemura University of Tokyo, master degree for biology(gene expression for brain).

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